

C0446 TARGETING PLASMOPARA VITICOLA PROTEASE INHIBITORS TO ENHANCE GRAPEVINE RESISTANCE AGAINST DOWNY MILDEW

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2 Text (Suggested structure: Objectives, Methods, Results and Conclusions (No Figures/Tables))

Downy mildew, caused by the oomycete *Plasmopara viticola*, remains one of the most significant threats to grapevine (*Vitis vinifera*) production worldwide, leading to extensive economic and environmental burdens due to chemical control. In line with the objectives of the Horizon 2020 SHIELD4GRAPE (S4G) project to develop sustainable strategies against fungal and oomycete pathogens, we identified and characterized *P. viticola* protease inhibitors that may interfere with grapevine's immune-related serine proteases.

We have inoculated five different grapevine cultivars, with distinct tolerance degrees to *P. viticola*, with two *P. viticola* isolates with contrasting aggressiveness. Using a comprehensive bioinformatics screening of the *P. viticola* genome database, we characterized the serine protease inhibitors family. An *in vitro* fluorescence-based proteolytic assay demonstrated that the proteolytic activity of serine proteases was lower when the most aggressive *P. viticola* isolate is present. qPCR analyses of identified *P. viticola* serine protease inhibitors at early infection time-points indicated that one of the *P. viticola* inhibitors was up-regulated in the most aggressive isolate. Finally, we explored the potential of a spray-induced gene silencing (SIGS) approach to block this specific *P. viticola* inhibitor. Remarkably, silencing this inhibitor compromised *P. viticola* sporulation, thereby highlighting its essential role in pathogen virulence. Our findings provide novel insights into the molecular basis of *P. viticola* pathogenesis and open avenues for novel control measures.

3 Keywords (up to a maximum of 3)

Protease; Protease inhibitors; Grapevine Downy Mildew

